

Method Development and Validation for Aspirin Quantification in Tablets: A Stability Indicating Method with EMC-11 UV Application

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Abstract:

A simple, sensitive, specific, precise and cost effective UV spectrophotometric EMC-11 was used to developed and validated method for determination of Aspirin (ASP) in pharmaceutical formulation and biological fluid. The maximum absorption of Aspirin was shown at 300 nm using methanol as a solvent. The linear calibration curve of aspirin concentrations range (10-80 ppm) are shown to show the regression equation ($Y = 0.0409x + 0.0015$), and correlation Coefficient ($R^2 = 0.9995$). %RSD showed an acceptable value for precision study less than 1%. Where LOD and LOQ value showed to be $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.02 and 0.08, respectively. Accuracy study showed good

recovery 99.8% in locally commercial tablets. The present developed method was successfully applied for stability-indicating of Aspirin in pure and tablets dosage form. Stability-indicating study was investigated under acidic, alkaline, oxidative, photolytic and thermal conditions. According to the resultants it can be concluded that the validated method can be used in routine analysis of Aspirin in tablets dosage form, biological fluid and degradation study.

Keywords: Aspirin, UV spectrophotometric EMC-11, Development and Validation, Quality Control and Stability-Indicating.

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Introduction

Aspirin (ASP) is chemically known as 2-acetoxybenzoic acid (Acetylsalicylic acid) Its molecular formula is $C_9H_8O_4$ as shown in figure 1, having molecular weight 180 g/mole (Acharya, et al., 2015). It is slightly soluble in water, freely soluble in alcohol, soluble in chloroform and ether, sparingly soluble in absolute ether. ASP is one of the first drugs to come into common usage, is still the most widely used drug in the world, is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug that exhibits anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antipyretic activities (Gousuddin, et al., 2016).

Figure 1. Chemical Structure of Aspirin (ASP)

In literature reviewing many analytical technique have been developed to described ASP can be determined individual or in combination with other medicine, such as UV-Vis spectrophotometry (Alhamdan, & Alfahad, 2021; Abdussalam-Mohammed, et al., 2024; Uzunović, & Topčagić, 2020), titrimetric (Anthony, et al., 2017; Chahal, 2022; Campanella, et al., 2010), GC-MS (El Haj, et al., 1999; Tsikas, et al., 1998), HPTLC (Damle, et al., 2009), and HPLC-UV (Gousuddin, et al., 2016; Kamal, Marie, & Hammad, 2020).

In the present study stability indicating HPLC method for the ASP was tested by degrading the drugs under various stress conditions like acid hydrolysis, alkaline hydrolysis, and oxidation, thermal and photolytic stress which is recommended by ICH guideline (Qasim, et al., 2024).

Materials and Methods

Chemical and Reagent

Pharmaceutically active ingredient (99 %purity) of ASP was purchased from Awa-medical Company in Kurdistan of Iraq. Commercial tablets of ASP which randomly purchased from local pharmacies are made in Kurdistan-Iraq. Grade reagents namely sodium hydroxide (NaOH), and hydrochloric acid (HCl), were purchased from Scharlau (Spain), while hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) were purchased from Roth (Germany). Solvents, acetonitrile, methanol, and water HPLC grade, were purchased from Merck (Germany).

Instrumentation

Spectrophotometric analysis was carried using UV-vis spectrophotometer EMC-11-UV, single-beam, with deuterium arc lamp, tungsten made in Germany. UV lamp (UVC-215 TS 8W, 220-240v, 50/6 Hz) was used for photo degradation study. The analytical balance was Voyager®. The water bath shaker was Elmasonic P (100W, 80 KHz) and the oven was Lab Tech (LVO-2030).

Method Development

The development of a method to determine the presence of ASP in various materials, such as tablets and biological fluid, is critical for both drug analysis and clinical diagnostics. The objective is to develop a dependable, precise, and replicable analytical technique capable of measuring the amount of ASP in various sample types. The UV-Vis spectrophotometer EMC-11-UV was chosen for this investigation due to its simplicity and cost-effectiveness.

Method Optimization

Method optimization is a critical step in analytical chemistry, ensuring that the developed method is robust, accurate, and reliable for the intended analysis (Qasim, & Mohammed, 2021). For the determination of aspirin in a tablet dosage form using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer EMC-11-UV, optimization involves fine-tuning experimental parameters to improve sensitivity, specificity, and reproducibility.

Selection of Wavelength (λ_{max})

Identifying the most effective wavelength for analyzing ASP is a critical step in developing a dependable spectrophotometric method. The wavelength at which a material demonstrates maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) is selected for quantitative investigation due to its superior sensitivity and accuracy. Used a scanning mode (200–400 nm) to confirm λ_{max} in the specific solvent being used.

Solvent Selection

The selection of a solvent in analytical chemistry is critical because it has a significant impact on the solubility of the analyte, the stability of the solution, and the analysis results. Depending on the analytical method, sample matrix, and specific analysis needs, many solvents can dissolve ASP. Optimize by testing different solvents and selecting one with minimal baseline noise and maximum solubility. Some common solvents often used include methanol, ethanol, and water.

Sample Preparation

Preparation of Standard and Sample Solutions

Precisely measured a solution of 100 mg of pure ASP was dissolved in methanol and then transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask. The remaining volume in the flask was filled with solvent to reach the mark, resulting in a stock standard solution with a concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The conventional solution of ASP was stored in a refrigerator and utilized to create various concentrations of working solutions.

Preparation of ASP standard working solutions:

A total of ten tablets (2 g) contain of 500 mg of ASP, were measured and then crushed into a fine powder. 0.4 gram of ASP tablet powder was precisely weighed and put into a 100 mL volumetric flask. The powder was dissolved by sonication for 20 minutes using an adequate amount of methanol. The volume was adjusted to the mark using methanol containing 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of ASP. The content was passed through a 0.45 μm nylon filter using Whatman filter paper. Working solutions at various

concentrations were produced from the stock solution of the formulation.

Method Validation

Validation is essential to ensure the analytical method is accurate, reliable, and suitable for its intended purpose. The validation process follows guidelines such as those set by the “International Conference on Harmonization (ICH Q2(R1))”. There are several parameters for validation including, specificity, linearity, precision, accuracy, LOD and LOQ, robustness, and stability.

Stability-Indicating Studies for Aspirin

Stability-indicating studies are critical to evaluate the degradation profile of aspirin under various stress conditions, ensuring the developed analytical method can separate aspirin from its degradation products. These studies are essential for determining shelf life and understanding the stability of aspirin formulations.

Acidic condition

To prepare 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ In 50 mL volumetric flask, 2.5 mL from the stock solution (1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) of drug was transferred and 2.5 mL of (0.1, 0.2 and 0.3)N of HCl was added, and then heated to 50°C. At the beginning 2 mL of this solution was taken at room temperature in to volumetric flask (10 mL). Then, another 2 mL from this solution was transferred into separate volumetric flask (10 mL) at different times up to 5 hrs. After neutralizing with a suitable reagent the total volume was completed with methanol to obtain 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of ASP.

Alkaline condition

The same procedure in section 2.5.1 was followed replacing (0.1, 0.2 and 0.3)N of HCl with (0.1, 0.2 and 0.3)N of NaOH.

Oxidation condition

The same procedure in section 2.5.1 was followed replacing (0.1, 0.2 and 0.3)N of HCl with (3, 6, 9) % of H_2O_2 .

Photo degradation

Three replicates of 2.5 mL from a stock solution (1000 µg/mL) of drug were transferred into 50 mL volumetric flasks to prepare three solutions containing 50 µg/mL of ASP. These solutions were exposed to different circumstances including sunlight, UV, and dark up to 48 Hrs. From each solution, 5 mL was transferred into 25 mL of volumetric flask, and the final volume was made up with methanol to form solution containing 10 µg/mL of ASP.

Thermal degradation

Accurate weight of 2.0 g (10 tablets) of drug was taken and powdered by mortar and then exposed in an oven at 80 °C up to 48 hrs. From this powdered, 0.04 mg of exposed drug was dissolved in methanol then transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask that was sonicated for 15 minutes and the final volume was made with methanol to form a solution containing 10 µg/mL of ASP.

Result and Discussion

Method Optimization

Developing and validating analytical method aims to confirm a suitable method for analysis a particular analyte with specific, accurate, and precise results. The main objective for that is to improve the conditions and parameters followed in the development and validation methods, therefore a wide variety of procedures need to be tested.

Scanning and determination of λ_{max}

The spectrum of ASP showed maximum absorption at 300 nm as shown in Figure 2. This wavelength was used later for all study measurements.

Type of Solvent

The effect of the solvent was studied testing different solvents namely water, methanol and ethanol. 1 mg of pure ASP was weighed and solubility was checked in 10 mL of solvent. Aspirin is more soluble in methanol than in water. This is because methanol, being an organic solvent, has a better ability to interact

with the nonpolar and slightly Polar Regions of the aspirin molecule compared to water, which is highly polar. The solubility of aspirin in methanol is generally higher due to the compatibility of similar polarities between the solvent and the solute.

Figure 2. Spectrum of ASP at Concentration (10 µg/mL)

Validation Results

Method validation is process for the collection and evaluation of data to establish precise evidence that the analytical method is capable of producing quality products (Qasim, Hamid, & Yousif, 2024). The developed method was validated according to ICH guidelines for the linearity, precision, accuracy, specificity, robustness, LOD and LOQ.

Linearity

The calibration of present method was investigated by determined at five concentration levels ranging (0.2-1.0 µg/mL) for ASP, the calibration curve was constructed by plotting absorbance versus concentrations of Aspirin (µg/mL) and the regression equation was calculated, linear absorbance data for calibration curve was shown in (Table 1, and Figure 3).

Figure 3. Calibration of Aspirin at Range 0.2-1.0 µg/mL

Table 1. Statistical Parameters of UV-VIS Determination of ASP

Statistical parameters	Value
Linear equation	$y = 0.0409x + 0.0015$
Slope (m)	0.0409
Intercept (b)	0.0015
Correlation Coefficient (R ²)	0.9995
Percentage Linearity (R ² %)	99.95
Intercept standard error	0.00370
LOD (µg/ml)	0.02 (µg/mL)
LOQ (µg/ml)	0.08(µg/mL)
Linearity range (µg/ml)	0.2-1.0 (µg/mL)

Precision

The precision was evaluated by deferent level of ASP concentration, each concentration repeat five time according to the condition of the type

of precession, repeatability, intra-day and inter-day. Table 2 shows RSD% values which are less than 1% indicating to good precision according to standard criteria of ICH.

Table 2. Evaluation Study of Precision

Type of precession	Level of concentration	RSD%
Repeatability	2.5 µg/mL	0.2
	5 µg/mL	0.6
	7.5 µg/mL	0.8
intra-day	2.5 µg/mL	0.4
	5 µg/mL	0.9
	7.5 µg/mL	0.7
inter-day	2.5 µg/mL	0.2
	5 µg/mL	0.6
	7.5 µg/mL	0.9

Accuracy and recovery

Evaluated the accuracy of the proposed method by analyzing a pure drug of ASP from excipients with known quantities of the drug. This resulted in solutions with concentrations of 5, 10, and 15 µg/mL for ASP, which correspond to 50, 100, and 150% of the expected analytical concentrations, respectively. The ASP values were obtained at concentrations of 4.9, 9.9, and 14.9 µg/mL, with relative standard deviations (RSD%) lower than 1.5%. The accuracy of the measurements was determined to be 99.54%, 99.01%, and 99.66% for the respective concentrations as shown in table 3. These results demonstrate that the procedure was accurate within the targeted range.

Table 3. Evaluation of Accuracy (Recovery) Study

Level of Recovery (%)	Added amount (µg/mL)	Conc. Obtained	Recovery%	Statistical Analysis		
				Mean (%)	SD	RSD%
50%	5	5.1	101.22	99.54	1.45	1.46
	5	4.9	98.73			
	5	4.9	98.68			
100%	10	10.0	99.71	99.01	0.72	0.73
	10	9.8	98.26			
	10	9.9	99.07			
150%	15	14.9	99.61	99.66	0.12	0.12
	15	15.0	99.80			
	15	14.9	99.58			

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ)

Limit of detection (LOD) of an analytical technique is the lowest concentration that can be detected and distinguished from zero but may not always be calculated as an exact measure. Whereas, limit of quantification (LOQ) is the lowest concentration of the analyte in a sample that can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy. LOD and LOQ were found using a linear regression model, as defined by the International Council for Harmonization (ICH). The LOD and LOQ were computed based on the slope and standard deviation of the intercept of the mean of three calibration curves. The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) achieved for ASP were 0.02 and 0.08 µg/mL, respectively. The developed method was found to be sensitive as shown in Table 1.

Specificity

An analytical method's specificity refers to its capacity to accurately measure the analyte's

response even when other substances are present, such as contaminants, degradation products, and matrix. The analytical placebo solution, which included all excipients except ASP, was prepared according to the sample preparation procedure. To determine the impact of these additives, which are non-active substances, a combination of standard solutions and commercially available pharmaceutical formulations of ASP was investigated using the validated method. The method's specificity was further assessed to confirm the absence of interference products that result from forced degradation. The present method's specificity was found to be 99.9% with RSD% lower than 1.5.

Robustness

In the proposed UV method, a small modification in wavelength (± 1 nm) was used to validate the robustness parameter. The data will be shown in Table 4. The relative standard deviation (RSD %) was below 1%, indicating a high level of robustness for the method.

Table 4. Robustness Study of the Method ± 1 nm

Sample	Absorbance				
	298 nm	299 nm	300 nm	301 nm	302 nm
Mean	0.4010	0.4014	0.4019	0.4017	0.4014
SD	0.0007	0.0005	0.0001	0.0005	0.0006
% RSD	0.1853	0.1263	0.0273	0.1173	0.1383

Analysis of marketing formulation

The improved method has been successfully implemented in the estimation ASP in marketing formulation. Recovery experiments were performed at three solutions of pure drug with

two other tablet formulations, in which the sample stock solutions were spiked with pure and tablet formulation solutions containing 10 µg/mL of the labelled amounts of drugs. The results are determined and summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Results of Marketing Products of ASP

Tablet formulation	Concentration added	Concentration Found	Recovery %	RSD %
Company 1	10 µg/mL	9.96	99.61	1.34
Company 2	10 µg/mL	9.97	99.68	1.12
Company 3	10 µg/mL	10.1	100.09	1.40
Company 4	10 µg/mL	9.9	99.03	1.05

Stability-Indicating Results

Studding of stability-indicating for the ASP pure and tablets dosage form contain (10 µg/ML) API of ASP, under various conditions, such as acid, alkaline, oxidation, photolytic, and thermal stress. Resultants in the table 6 show that ASP under Basic Conditions (NaOH) lead to faster and more extensive degradation compared to

acidic conditions, because the hydroxide ion is a stronger nucleophile than water, accelerating the hydrolysis of the ester bond in aspirin. However degradation of ASP occurred in all stress condition except in dark photolytic condition as shown in table 6. This result indicates that ASP very sensitive drug when exposed to their stress condition of stability-indicating.

Table 6. Results of stability-indicating products of the method

Stress condition/ duration/ state		% Degradation					Observation
		Pure	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	
Acidic	0.1N/2hrs	9.1	9	8.7	8.9	9.2	Degrade
	0.2N/2hrs	9.0	8.4	8.7	8.6	9.0	Degrade
	0.3N/2hrs	9.1	8.8	8.6	8.4	8.5	Degrade
Alkaline	0.1N/2hrs	9.3	9.0	8.9	9.0	8.7	Degrade
	0.2N/2hrs	9.1	8.4	8.5	8.4	8.3	Degrade
	0.3N/2hrs	9.0	8.0	7.8	7.5	7.4	Degrade
Oxidative	3% H ₂ O ₂ /2hrs	8.9	8.6	8.4	8.1	8.3	Degrade
	6% H ₂ O ₂ / 2hrs	7.5	7.8	7.9	7.4	7.0	Degrade
	9% H ₂ O ₂ /2hrs	6.5	6.4	6.1	6.2	6.1	Degrade
Photo	48 hrs/solid Sun	9.8	9.6	9.5	9.5	9.6	Slight discoloration
	48 hrs/solid Dark	9.9	9.8	9.8	9.9	10	No photo degradation
	48 hrs/solid UV	9.3	9.2	9.3	9.0	9.2	Noticeable discoloration
Thermal	80°C/48 hrs.	8.9	8.8	8.9	8.7	9.0	Degrade

Conclusion

A simple stability indicating UV-Vis spectrophotometer EMC-11-UV method for the simultaneous determination of aspirin (ASP) in bulk and in its pharmaceutical dosage forms has been described for the first time. The proposed method was successfully validated in terms of system suitability, linearity, precision, accuracy, selectivity, specificity, LOD, LOQ and robustness as per the guidelines of ICH. The results of validation parameters were found to be within the acceptable limits. The results of forced degradation studies showed that the proposed method is stability indicating and capable of simultaneous quantification of aspirin in the presence of their degradation products.

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